

Dietitians' Perspectives on the Nutritional Management of Infantile Colic and Constipation

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Background:

Functional gastrointestinal disorders, colic and constipation, occur in ~50% of infants, with prevalence between 3-40% (colic) and 3-27% (constipation). Aetiology is multifactorial with nutritional and non-nutritional therapies existing. 'Comfort formula', foods for special medical purposes (FSMPs), are marketed for dietary management of colic and constipation.

Aim:

Investigate knowledge, beliefs, and practices of dietitians in Ireland regarding dietary management of colic and constipation, its diagnostic criteria, and 'Comfort Formula' use.

Research Design:

A rapid review examined 'Comfort Formula' use in practice. A survey of Irish dietitians assessed demographics, knowledge, clinical exposure, attitudes, and confidence. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests and Spearman's correlation (SPSS; $p < 0.05$).

Results:

Diagnostic features that were widely identified were "rule of threes" for colic (32/36, 88.9%) and infrequent or hard stools for constipation (33/36, 91.7%). There was disagreement that 'Comfort formula' is effective in managing colic 15/27 (55.6%) or constipation 16/27 (59.3%). Proportionality, 'Comfort formula' were 'infrequently' recommending for colic 21/29 (72.4%) or constipation 22/29 (75.9%), with non-nutritional management strategies favoured, such as parental reassurance/education for colic (27/28, 96.4%) and use of laxatives/fibre for constipation (21/28, 75.0%). Conversely, respondents reported encountering infants consuming FSMPs for colic (22/36, 61.2%) and constipation (20/36, 55.5%) without prior medical supervision.

Conclusion:

Dietitians favoured non-nutritional management over recommendation of 'Comfort formula' revealing a divide between regulatory requirements requiring the use of FSMPs under medical supervision and carer initiation of FSMP consumption. Enhanced guidance, parental education, and further research is warranted to understand FSMP usage and to support evidence-based management.

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